

How student collaboration influence on student success

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Abstract

This report regarded student success in higher education that is with high importance and one of the main concern for all institutes. It reviews how student success can be enhanced using collaboration tools in VLE and the methods that are used. The base types of collaboration are described too. The features of effective learning environment that result to higher student success are discussed. The report analyzes the experience of Faculty of Technique and Technology - Yambol from Thracian University according to the EU DigComp 2.1 framework and the competences that the students should acquire for communication and collaboration.

Keywords: students collaboration, student success, effective learning environment

1. Introduction

The most effective educators are those who make their lessons easy to be love and help students love learning again, and always, and that is the greatest gifts, which teacher can give to scholars (Lee, 2018a). The methods that can enhance student success, recognized from US institutions, and that will be in priority in 2018, according to Zewald (2017), are:

- ✓ *Closer collaboration between higher institutions;*
- ✓ *Enrollment targets best-fit students;*
- ✓ *Organizational structures evolve to support student success – implementation of new advising models to enhance student success;*
- ✓ *Increased tech investments - continued increase in tech investment to support student success, spending on software for academic advising and planning;*
- ✓ *Standard commercial software use - use of standard commercial software rather than custom development;*
- ✓ *Integrated system approaches - many institutions found that their legacy student information systems harder adapt to new models, hampering admissions and advancement efforts, which discourages collaboration and undermines data integrity. A new approach to core systems are starting to emphasis across the entire student lifecycle;*
- ✓ *Rise of data warehouse and analytics - predictive analytics is an area of analytics that more schools will utilize to find and retain students;*
- ✓ *Automation focus - automation in core systems to support early alerts and action plans for at-risk students and to reduce repetitive tasks and keep processes agile that helps academic institutions to better support students. Academic advisors will be able to use technology that facilitates automation to identify at-risk students faster. This will help them to provide a clear action plan for improving overall success;*
- ✓ *Mobile and self-service student experiences - more focus on student portals, self-service and mobile app development;*

- ✓ *Increased use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM)* - focused on strategies that build strong employer branding partnerships a vital factor in a student's decision to apply to a university as its reputation;
- ✓ *Growing artificial intelligence (AI) awareness* - post-secondary educational institutions to use AI-enabled tools to drive student success. For example, to register for classes and to apply for financial aid using a *chatbot*;
- ✓ *Core SIS replacement trend* - to report student success outcomes.

The purpose of article is to review how can use the collaboration tools in VLE and different types of collaboration that enhance a student success. The main characteristics of effective learning environment that result to higher student success are discussed too.

2. Thracian e-University

In Trakia University the students and teachers have the opportunity to be registered online at the existing data base, www.trakia-uni.bg, and to have access to a personal e-mail and Integrated Management and Information System (Nedeva&Karabaliev, 2017).

As a result of implementation of blended learning as a regular method for teaching in Trakia University of Stara Zagora, Thracian e-University has been created with e-courses covered nearly all disciplines in curriculum on Moodle learning platform (<http://edu.uni-sz.bg/>). With a new e-data base, students have the opportunity to use free of charge e-virtual library, multimedia e-books, presentations, quizzes, on-line knowledge assessment, academic schedule, chats, forums, and site for useful student information that support student collaboration and success.

The skills for communication and collaboration as part of EU DigComp 2.1 framework (Carretero et al, 2017) are:

- ✓ *Interacting through digital technologies* - to interact through a variety of digital technologies and to understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context;
- ✓ *Sharing through digital technologies* - to share data, information and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies; to act as an intermediary, to know about referencing and attribution practices;
- ✓ *Engaging in citizenship through digital technologies* - to participate in society through the use of public and private digital services; to seek opportunities for self-empowerment and for participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies;
- ✓ *Collaborating through digital technologies* - to use digital tools and technologies for collaborative processes, and for co-construction and co-creation of resources and knowledge;
- ✓ *Netiquette* - to be aware of behavioral norms and know-how while using digital technologies and interacting in digital environments. To adapt communication strategies to the specific audience and to be aware of cultural and generational diversity in digital environments.
- ✓ *Managing digital identity* - to create and manage one or multiple digital identities, to be able to protect one's own reputation, to deal with the data that one produces through several digital tools, environments and services.

In the Thracian e-University, various forms of work and cooperation of students have been created and used in applied faculty courses and disciplines. The most used ones are Workshop, Chat, Forum and Wiki. They develop skills and learning experiences in digital collaboration, digital sharing, digital engagement, and digital collaboration.

To acquire and apply skills for communication and collaboration, along with the above mentioned forms, we offer training for ECDL (European Computer Driving License) certificates in the e-learning environment of the Thracian e-University. The ECDL Foundation defines Quality

Assurance Standards, which all national operators must adhere to in the implementation and promotion of our certification programs (ECDL Foundation, 2018). National operator for Bulgaria is ECDL - Bulgaria (ECDL Bulgaria, 2018). The Faculty of Techniques and Technologies - Yambol at Thracian University has a certified and authorized training and testing center. The materials are organized in e-course "ECDL" in Thracian e-University. Training sessions are unified for all 24,000 test centers in 148 countries around the world. They are designed, validated and approved by academic and industry experts from around the world. Knowledge and practical training for collaboration and communication are covered in Base, Intermediate and Advanced Modules. Specific training in this direction is provided by the students in Intermediate modules - IT security, Online Collaboration and Project Planning. In addition to the competences they acquire through the assignments in the training courses, Netiquette and managing digital identity are covered in these courses.

3. Enhancing student success in higher education

Key priorities for learning and teaching in higher education are focused on enhancing student success and included thematic areas of strategic importance to any institution: *assessment; employability; student engagement; access, retention, attainment and progression; flexible learning, and internationalization* (fig. 1, HEA 2016).

The frameworks (fig. 1) have an impact upon student success by influencing on:

- ✓ *HE curricula* - content, design, delivery and documenting of the formal and/or informal curricula;
- ✓ *Learning environments* - design and provision of formal and/or informal learning spaces and resources;
- ✓ *Learning communities* - widening and engaging staff and students in professional, academic and discipline communities;
- ✓ *Teaching quality* - quality of design, delivery or evaluation of teaching as core to the enhancement of any theme or discipline.

Figure 1. Student Success Framework (HEA, 2016)

4. Collaboration and student success

The collaboration is a driving force to improve student success (Burns et al., 2015). Success means different things to different students (HEA, 2016). There are five types of students' study profiles that differ in their learning success (Asikainen et al, 2003):

- ✓ *deep approach to learning;*
- ✓ *deep approach to learning, but poor time management;*
- ✓ *fact-based learning and repetition before understanding;*
- ✓ *change from understanding to memorization in the course;*
- ✓ *surface approach to learning.*

Nevertheless, there are many evidences that the collaboration of students in the process of study leads to better understanding, achieving higher levels of learning and retaining more new information working in a group rather than individually (Gokhale, 1995; Johnson & Johnson, 1986; Davis, 2012). Students are capable of performing at higher intellectual levels when asked to work in collaborative situations (Vygotsky, 1978). It was registered that a collaborative study has helped students to achieve greater academic success (Davis M., 2012; Burns et al., 2015), and enhances students' interest to study (Queenie et al, 2015). Collaboration spurs innovation bringing together different ideas, approaches, experiences, and creating a productive environment for generating new concepts and methods (Burns et al., 2015). Collaborative learning is a very important in achieving a critical thinking (Gokhale, 1995). Moreover, working in a team is an important mechanism for dealing with changing business environment; team learning is an attempt to prepare students to real-world experiences (Yazici, 2005).

The collaboration in learning has three things in common: *shared knowledge, shared knowing and shared responsibility* (Tinto, 2003). The results of investigations showed that a higher student success was achieved when a learning management system was combined with advanced collaborative tools during the teaching in a Web-based environment (Nadir et al, 2007). In a highly effective learning environment (fig.2), the learning is a collaborative and harmonious process, and teachers and students are happy and focused (Lee, 2018b). The things considered as an essential for creating an ideal learning environment is shown in fig.2 (Lee, 2018b).

Figure 2. The 10 Characteristics of a Highly Effective Learning Environment (Lee, 2018b)

The students are collaborated in education by asking questions, by development of application and reporting of assessment as much as possible (Lee, 2018b).

The core attributes of successful learning teams are (Varlas, 2010):

- ✓ *shared values and goals;*
- ✓ *collective responsibility;*
- ✓ *authentic assessment;*
- ✓ *self-directed reflection;*
- ✓ *stable settings;*
- ✓ *strong leadership support.*

Through collaboration a unique opportunity of helping each other to learn are created (Dreon, 2013). In order to be successful in a collaborative environment, the students must learn to communicate freely and directly, supporting and value each participant's contribution. The collaborative groups must be heterogeneous and to contain: *different genders; different ethnicities; participants that prefer different subjects; that do not know each other very well; have different "intelligences"; have varying levels of academic and technology proficiency* (Bias & Kolk, 2018).

Collaboration interinstitutional and interindividual is a powerful tool to promote learning and professional growth, it is an important way to innovate and adapt the education in a time of rapid and continuous change (Baldwin & Chang, 2007). In order the collaboration to be successful the following activities are needed:

- ✓ *choosing the partners carefully* - a successful collaboration increase when potential partners get to know each other, possess common interests, and identify similar purposes and goals;
- ✓ *never underestimate the importance of socialization* - conditions that promote conversation are important;
- ✓ *monitor progress and assess outcomes* - collaborations are dynamic entities, collaborators should periodically take stock of how things are going, identify challenges, and work to resolve conflicts;
- ✓ *be flexible* - partners should be flexible, when a collaboration does not work as planned.

Learning is a major incentive for collaborating. The key elements of successful collaborations are *trust, communication, a sense of shared interests and goals, and defined and clear expectations and roles*. The organizations are seeking to learn about the newest or "best" practices and to apply to their own situations. The collaboration opportunities included: *Co-mentoring projects; Scholarly consultation grants; Support for collaborative research; Research/student assistants; Field/interest-based conferences and workshops; Support for intellectual community; and Leadership development* (Baldwin & Chang, 2007).

Conclusion

The policy of being transparent, sharing knowledges, "best" practices and circumstances, working in partnership on projects and in different areas in education are applied intensively nowadays. The collaboration increases the prosperity of any institution and enhances the student success.

The Faculty of Techniques and Technologies assesses the role of the virtual environment and the new technologies in order to create better conditions in which the knowledge and skills for communication and collaboration are learned. They are an important prerequisite for enhancing student achievement through collaborative assignments, mutual evaluation, and teacher support in the virtual learning environment.

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